

ESiWACE3 Newsletter

Issue #4 / May 2024

News

Call for Proposals 2024

A new [Call for Proposals](#) (CfP) to apply for the services provided by ESiWACE3 has been opened. On this occasion, two types of services can be required:

- **Service 1** "Collaborations to prepare Europe's Weather and Climate Models for pre-exascale Systems": This service offers collaborative projects in which ESiWACE experts provide advice and engineering effort to the applicant. It aims to support the exascale preparations for the European Earth-System Models (ESM) community.
- **Service 2** "Services on state-of-the-art development tools for Weather and Climate": This service offers support for tools developed by ESiWACE partners. It aims to support the exascale preparations for the European Earth-System Models (ESM) community.

The call is open to all groups developing and maintaining ESM codes until 3 June 2024.

For more information, please visit our [Service Calls section](#).

The graphic features the ESiWACE logo at the top left. Below it, the title 'CALL FOR PROPOSALS 2024' is centered in blue. Two columns are separated by a vertical green line. The left column is titled 'Service 1' in orange and describes preparing weather and climate models for pre-exascale systems, accompanied by a globe icon. The right column is titled 'Service 2' in orange and describes state-of-the-art development tools for weather and climate, accompanied by a wrench and screwdriver icon. Both columns specify a duration and a deadline of 3 June 2024. At the bottom, there are logos for the European Union and EuroHPC, and a URL for more information: <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/software-support/service-calls>.

Showcase services videos

Latest Thinking, the audiovisual company expert in scientific communication and part of the ESiWACE3 Consortium joined members of the services and the communication work packages to elaborate some videos to promote further the services provided by the ESiWACE3 experts and encourage people to apply for them. In these videos, recipients of services during the previous phase of ESiWACE explained their cases and how the help of our experts contributed to improving their research and solving their problems. Also, the ESiWACE experts who provided these services explained how they experienced it and what lessons they learned from these projects.

You can watch the interviews directly on our [YouTube channel](#).

We hope you like them and encourage you to request [our services](#) if you need them!

ESIWACE3 with the Digital EU Ambassadors

On 6 March 2024, the Barcelona Supercomputing Center-Centro Nacional de Supercomputación (BSC-CNS, ESIWACE3's coordinator) received the visit of EuroHPC Joint Undertaking and Digital EU representatives, as well as Digital EU Ambassadors to learn about European funded initiatives and MareNostrum5.

ESIWACE3's PI, Mario Acosta, was asked to explain the use of HPC to perform climate and weather modelling. The audience was interested in the project and how the pre-exascale supercomputers can help fight climate change. It was an honour for the ESIWACE3 Consortium to be chosen as representative of the EuroHPC JU CoEs.

8 March - International Women's Day

On International Women's Day, celebrated on the 8th of March, the ESIWACE3 Consortium wanted to take advantage of the opportunity to give voice to (some of) the women of our Center of Excellence.

You can recover [here](#) our little tribute, wishing to help forge a better, more inclusive world for women.

Happy International Women's Day! 💜

esiwace
CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE IN SIMULATION OF WEATHER AND CLIMATE IN EUROPE

*Equity will be achieved when
we focus on the individual
rather than the barriers that
divide us.*

Mar Rodríguez
Project Manager Officer at the
Barcelona Supercomputing
Center (BSC)

#WomenInESIWACE3
#8MESIWACE3

Co-funded by
the European Union

EuroHPC

2nd ESiWACE3 Hackathon

On 24-26 June 2024, Amsterdam (Netherlands) will hold the 2nd ESiWACE3 Hackathon. Entitled “Optimisation and Tuning of Earth-System Models”, the event targets weather and climate modellers at all career stages and aims to assist climate scientists with optimising earth-system models (ESMs). It will be an on-site event at the [Netherlands eScience Center](#) (in Amsterdam), and remote participation is impossible.

The hackathon is designed so that participants bring their codes and work in teams, together with HPC experts, to improve the performance of their code. In the context of the optimisation and tuning of ESMs, the focus of this hackathon is on (but not limited to) porting of code to Graphics Processing Units (GPUs), performance portability on different architectures, use of auto-tuning for performance optimisation or energy-efficiency, and application of mixed-precision programming techniques.

The applicant’s institution needs to be located in one of the countries participating in the [EuroHPC Joint Undertaking](#) or belong to the list of [Inclusiveness Target Countries](#). Groups with early career scientists and female researchers are especially encouraged to apply.

For more information, visit the [event website](#).

1st ESiWACE-Warm World Summer School

The first of the summer schools to be organised by ESiWACE3 has already dates and venue: 27 August - 2 September 2024, in Helsinki (Finland). Organised jointly by [ESiWACE3](#) and the [German BMBF project WarmWorld](#), the “HPC for Climate and Weather Applications” summer school aims to bring together young researchers and software engineers interested in the current technological developments in climate modelling. Together, they will explore hot topics in high-performance computing for climate and weather applications.

It will be an on-site event at the [Hotelli Korpilampi](#) near Helsinki, with no possibility of remote participation. The participants will attend lectures and practical sessions, guiding them through the fundamentals of performing weather and climate simulations on modern HPC systems and managing and analysing Earth system model data.

The programme is aimed at advanced master's and doctoral students in the early phases of their PhD in applied maths, informatics and natural sciences. Particular encouragement is given to women and participants from the [ITC countries](#) to apply for the Summer School!

For more information about lecturers, sessions, fees, and registration, visit the [event website](#).

Events

Internal events

Review

On Monday, February 19, 2024, the ESiWACE3 Consortium travelled to the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking facilities in Luxembourg to attend its 1st Project Review. The meeting started at 9:30 am at the Ariane Building, with a brief presentation of the project by the CoE coordinator, Mario Acosta (Barcelona Supercomputing Center, BSC). Then, each of the Work Packages presented a brief summary of the work carried out during the period under review. Most of the WP leaders attended the meeting in person and had the opportunity to answer questions from the project manager, Mladen bla bla, and the expert reviewers, [Dr Alexander Vapirev](#), [Dr Iris Pantle](#), and [Dr Esther Andrés Perez](#). A short discussion session closed the event.

The ESiWACE3 Consortium was delighted to exchange views and opinions with the PO and the reviewers and would like to thank the EuroHPC Board for their warm welcome, as well as the PO and the experts for their helpful and constructive comments.

External events

External events in which ESIWACE3 has participated since the last issue of the ESIWACE Newsletter:

- [PinT 2024 - 13th Workshop on Parallel-in-Time Integration](#), Bruges (Belgium), 6 February 2024. Keynote presentation.
- EU Digital Ambassadors and EuroHPC JU representatives visit, Barcelona (Spain), 6 March 2024. Invited presentation
- [EuroHPC Summit 2024](#), Antwerp (Belgium), 18-22 March 2024. Presentation & Poster
- [FDO Summit 2024](#), Berlin (Germany), 20-21 March 2024. Presentation
- [NCC Netherlands and NCC Italy meeting](#), Bologna (Italy) & remote, 02 April 2024. Presentation
- [UN Ocean Decade Conference Off-site parallel event](#), Barcelona (Spain), 08 April 2024. Presentation
- [UN Ocean Decade Conference](#), Barcelona (Spain), 10-12 April 2024. Video.
- [4th Baltic HPC and Cloud Computing Conference](#), Riga (Latvia), 11-12 April 2024. Slide & Video.
- [EGU 2024](#), Vienna (Austria), 14-19 April 2024. Slide & Poster.
- [EGU 2024](#), Vienna (Austria), 14-19 April 2024. Presentation.
- [Scalable Parallel Computing Lab](#) (SPCL), Zürich (Switzerland), 4 April 2024. Seminar.
- [Gauss Centre for Supercomputing](#), Jülich (Germany), 16 April 24. Invited talk.
- [Climate Informatics 2024](#), London (UK), 23 April 2024. Presentation.

Updates

During M14-M16 (February, March and April 2024), no ESIWACE3 Deliverable or Milestone was published.

News from the neighbours

Upcoming conferences and events

- [HPCKP Annual Meeting](#), 8-9 May 2024, Barcelona (Spain).
- [ISC24](#), 12-16 May 2024, Hamburg (Germany).
- [Teratec](#), 29-30 May 2024, Paris (France).
- [Advanced Computational Methods for Climate Modeling and Analysis minisymposium](#), 10-14 June 2024, Pilsen (Czech Republic).
- [Austrian-Slovenian HPC Meeting \(ASHPC24\)](#), 10-13 June 2024, Seeblickhotel Grundlsee (Austria)
- [Digital Ocean Forum](#), 14-15 June, 2024, Brussels (Belgium).
- [Workshop on Advancements of Global Challenges Applications \(PPAM2024\)](#), 8-11 September 2024, Ostrava (Czech Republic).
- [European Meteorology Society annual meeting](#), 2-6 September 2024, Barcelona (Spain).

Training events

Find collected information on upcoming and past training events from all consortium partners and projects we are involved with [here](#).

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To receive the latest news about ESIWACE3 in your email inbox, subscribe to the [ESIWACE3 Community](#).

You can also look at the [previous issues](#) of the ESIWACE newsletter.